

Integration of Microwave Resonant Sensors and Machine Learning Modeling for Advanced Characterization of Magnetodielectric Composites

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Additive manufacturing has created significant interest in the development of next-generation RF/microwave devices, including antennas, filters, and phase shifters, with a specific emphasis on innovative materials such as magneto-dielectrics (MD). Several methods, such as waveguides, microstrip transmission lines, and resonant structures like split-ring resonators (SRR), have been utilized to characterize MD materials and extract their permittivity (ϵ) and permeability (μ) values. However, these approaches encounter limitations in characterizing MD materials with non-zero complex permeability, often relying on separate polynomial expressions for ϵ and μ , thereby neglecting their intrinsic correlation.

In this study, we fabricated a series of MD composites with varying concentrations of Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles embedded in a PDMS matrix. To determine the ϵ and μ parameters, we propose a novel SRR sensor and a parameter extraction procedure utilizing Artificial Neural Networks (ANNs). This sensor is designed to stimulate two distinct regions that concentrate electric and magnetic fields differently, facilitating the excitation of these fields in a single measurement on a single sample. Consequently, the need to relocate the Sample Under Test (SUT) is eliminated, thereby mitigating the associated errors.

The obtained results demonstrate the effectiveness of the proposal in evaluating the manufacturing process of MD compounds. It is remarkable that the integration of SRRs and ANN modeling for characterizing MD material manufacturing suggests the potential extension of this technique to other nanoparticle compound formulations. Thus, this approach could guide manufacturing processes to align microwave properties more effectively with the resulting material characterization [1].

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